

Synthesis of some New Biquinolines

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A perusal of literature on biquinolines revealed that hydrogenated derivatives of biquinolines exhibit antioxidant activity for olefin polymers¹. Biquinolines are synthesised through Ullmann synthesis on haloquinolines², from the diamino-biphenyls by Skraup synthesis³ and by other methods⁴.

The present work deals with the synthesis of tetramethoxy 5,5',6,6'- and 7,7'-biquinolines and 6,6'-biquinoline ether by building up the required heterosystem around a prebuilt biphenyl moiety. 6,6',8,8'-Tetramethoxy-5,5'-biquinoline (**1a**), 5,5',8,8'-tetramethoxy-6,6'-biquinoline (**1b**), 6,6',8,8'-tetramethoxy-7,7'-biquinoline (**1c**) and 6,6'-biquinoline ether (**2**) were synthesised by the application of Skraup synthesis on appropriate diaminobiphenyl derivatives and 4,4'-diaminobiphenyl ether. The structures of these compounds have been established on the basis of elemental analysis, nmr and mass spectral studies.

Experimental

M.ps. were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Pmr spectra (CDCl₃) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz) spectrophotometer using TMS as an internal standard. The homogeneity and purity of the compounds were tested through tlc.

General methods : A mixture of the appropriate diamine (0.001 mol), anhydrous glycerol (0.002 mol), nitrobenzene (1 ml), ferrous sulphate (20 mg) and concentrated H₂SO₄ (1 ml) was heated in an oil-bath at 130–40° for 2 h. The reaction

mixture was cooled, diluted with water and excess of nitrobenzene was removed by steam distillation. It was then filtered and the filtrate was basified with alkali and the resulting solid was purified by passing through a column and crystallised from benzene : 6,6',8,8'-tetramethoxy-5,5'-biquinoline (**1a**; 300 mg, 80%), m.p. 265° (Found : C, 70.16; H, 5.72; N, 7.90, C₂₂H₂₀O₄N₂ requires : C, 70.21; H, 5.32; N, 7.44%); δ (CDCl₃) 3.95 (s, 4 × aromatic methoxy protons), 7.1–7.45 (m, H-3, H-3', H-7 and H-7'); the

(1a)

(1b)

singlet due to H-7 merged with the multiplet due to H-3 and H-3'), 8.0 (d, $J_{4,3}$ 9 Hz, H-4 and H-4'), 8.6 (d, $J_{2,3}$ 5 Hz, $J_{2,4}$ 2 Hz, H-2 and H-2'); 5,5',8,8'-tetramethoxy-6,6'-biquinoline (**1b**; 210 mg, 70%), m.p. 155° (Found : C, 69.89; H, 4.98; N, 7.15. $C_{22}H_{20}O_4N_2$ requires : C, 70.21; H, 5.32; N, 7.44%); δ 3.85 (12H, s, 4 \times OCH₃), 7.15–7.45 (4H, m, H-3, H-3', H-7, H-7'), 8.0 (2H, d, $J_{4,3}$ 9 Hz, H-4 and H-4'), 8.7 (2H, dd, $J_{2,3}$ 5 Hz, $J_{2,4}$ 2 Hz, H-2 and H-2'); 6,6',8,8'-tetramethoxy-7,7'-biquinoline (**1c**; 298 mg, 80%), m.p. 214° (Found : C, 70.40; H, 5.61; N, 7.82. $C_{22}H_{20}O_4N_2$ requires : C, 70.21; H, 5.32; N, 7.44%); δ 3.9 (12H, s, 4 \times OCH₃), 7.1–7.4 (4H, m, H-3, H-3', H-5 and H-5'), 7.85 (2H, d, $J_{4,3}$ 9 Hz, H-4'), 8.55 (2H, dd, $J_{2,3}$ 5 Hz, $J_{2,4}$ 2 Hz, H-2, H-2'); 6,6'-biquinoline ether (**2**; 205 mg, 75%),

m.p. 78° (Found : C, 79.41; H, 4.41; N, 10.29. $C_{18}H_{12}N_2O$ requires : C, 79.87; H, 4.65; N, 10.20%); δ 7.2–7.6 (6H, m, H-3, H-3', H-5, H-5', H-7, H-7'), 8.0 (4H, dd, $J_{4,3}$ 9 Hz, $J_{8,7}$ 10 Hz, H-4, H-4', H-8, H-8'), 8.80 (2H, dd, $J_{2,3}$ 6 Hz, $J_{2,4}$ 2 Hz, H-2, H-2'); m/z M^+ 272 (100%). Protons at 2,2', 4,4' and 8,8' resonated downfield as a result of deshielding by the nitrogen and protons at 3 and 3' resonated at the highest field strengths, consistent with the highest electron density at this position.

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